

Development of a Kamrupian Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS) course

Author(s): Rupam Das^{1,2}, Pranjal Das^{1,2}, Sonali Das^{1,2,5}, Sailen Ch. Baishya^{1,2}, Prajña Paramita Dutta^{1,2}, Tutumoni Baishya^{1,2}, Raunak Raj Singh^{1,2}, Lekhika Pathak^{1,2,3,4}, Dr. Pranab Jyoti Sarma^{1,2}, Bikul Das^{1,2,3,4,5*}

¹Centre for Vedic Altruism, KaviKrishna Laboratory, IIT-Guwahati Research Park, Guwahati, Assam, India.

²Department of Medical Humanities, KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care, Sualkuchi, Assam, India.

³Department of Cancer and Stem Cell Biology, KaviKrishna Laboratory, Research Park, Indian Institute of Technology, Guwahati, India.

⁴School of Agro and Rural Technology, Indian Institute of Technology, Guwahati, India.

⁵Thoreau Laboratory for Global Health, University of Massachusetts, Lowell, Massachusetts.

Sonalisdas14@gmail.com,
rupamslkdas@gmail.com,
dutta.prajna@gmail.com,
raunakrajsingh2861996@gmail.com,
pdtezucse@gmail.com,
tutu.monibaishya@gmail.com,
sbsualkuchi@gmail.com,
pathaklekhika29@gmail.com,
madhyaman@gmail.com

*Corresponding author, Email: bdas@kavikrishnalab.org

Introduction:

KaviKrishna is a SIRO-certified, nonprofit organization located in the Kamrup district of Assam, officially established in 2010. However, the organization unofficially began as the ‘Krishna Samaj’ in the 1920s, with the

aim of uplifting the local philosophy, weavers, and community. In its objective to turn its ‘Kavi’ (Vision) into ‘Krishna’ (Action), whether on a scientific, philosophical, or communal level, it draws inspiration from the ancient knowledge system that was prevalent in the temple-centric network of Kamrupa. Considering the impending complications of epidemics and climate change in which global supply chains are at risk, it is paramount to study and implement an economic structure that is both effective and self-reliant. Therefore, in consonance with the recent mandate made by the UGC, KaviKrishna is looking to use its platform in Sualkuchi as well as its academic research work and Muga revival efforts to develop a comprehensive course on the Indigenous Knowledge System.

Background:

In India, especially Assam, ‘Village-based economies’ are generally agrarian. In these societies, daily life is interwoven with worship, hence the existence of temple-based networks. Traces of Muga silk have been found along the Vedic Silk Road, which stretches from Kashgar, China to the Angkor Temple Complex in Cambodia. Additionally, gau-shalas (cow sheds) used to be present at many local temples. This interconnection between worship, economics, and agriculture, is the key concept behind the Indigenous Knowledge System, and as such, it shall be emphasized in KaviKrishna’s IKS coursework.

Methodology:

The Indigenous Knowledge System of Kamrup, part of the over-encompassing Indian Knowledge System, exists both on the theoretical level as well as the practical. Thus, the coursework aims to have two components: a theoretical, knowledge-based aspect, and a practical, field-based aspect. The areas of study include, but are not limited to: Muga silk, cow science, herbal medicine, and Jiva Upakara Tantra (an ancient tantric healing method of the Sualkuchi-Hajo region).

- 1) KaviKrishna aims to incorporate a theoretical course on Muga to the local colleges as part of the overarching IKS coursework, as well as establish its Living Muga Museum as a field-study site for students to gain practical experience and knowledge. Students will write assignments on Muga and analyze its importance in the history of Sualkuchi, as well as be encouraged to think innovatively in its relevance to the future, whether that be academic research on its properties such as cancer and UV protection, on its artistic and cultural value, etc.
- 2) KaviKrishna is setting up a similar model for cow science. On a theoretical level, students will learn the relevance and history of the cow. On a practical level, they will learn how to prepare organic compost out of cow dung, how to prepare Ghee (clarified butter) from milk etc. By involving the local youth of the Sualkuchi area in milk product production, teaching them about Whey protein production, marketing, maintenance, and logistics, innovative entrepreneurship will be encouraged.
- 3) Coursework on the theoretical knowledge of herbal medicine will be given, and practical work on cultivating herbal plants will be provided. The interconnection between cow dung and cow urine and herbal medicine will be emphasized to develop a bio plant that uses bio manure.
- 4) Jiva Upakara Tantra, the ancient tantric philosophy of Kamrup, will be taught on a theoretical level. A current book 'Reviving the Spirit of Jiva Upakra Tantra' is available.

Results:

KaviKrishna currently has a Living Muga Museum and a weaving network of 50 weavers. Since 2018, the U.G. students from Sualkuchi Budram Madhav Satradhikar College have been provided with course materials, assignments etc. regarding Muga silk and its production. They have been also given practical demonstrations and till now, we have received more than 30 assignments from the students. KaviKrishna also already has a herbal garden and is conducting research on their medicinal properties. The book on Jiva Upakra Tantra is currently being revised. Most other work regarding these projects is under preliminary development.

Conclusion:

Educating the youth on the Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS) is an important step in reviving the IKIN (Indigenous Kamrupian information network) which is based on the temple network of Kamrup. Such a task requires a multifaceted approach, and yet, has large ramifications. Simultaneously protecting the history and culture of the past while protecting the community against the future of pandemics and climate change, KaviKrishna aims to develop a sustainable and intricate model on how to systematically revive the IKS.